

Prevalence of sleep disturbance in Chinese healthcare professionals increases Eastward

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Dear Editors,

Borisenkov [1] took data by Qiu *et al.* [2] on the prevalence of sleep disturbance among Chinese healthcare professionals and contrasted them with the position in time zone (PTZ, longitude offset relative to the Beijing meridian, 115°E) to report that “when moving away from the Beijing meridian by 10° to the left or right, there is an increase in the frequency of detection of sleep disturbances by 6.5%”. Later, Johnson and Malow [3] used this result as one evidence of the chronic hazards associated with daylight saving time (DST). However, we want to highlight that results from Borisenkov [1] actually show an increase of the prevalence when moving away to the right (Eastward) of the Beijing meridian, so that DST would reduce the hazards.

Borisenkov [1] fits the prevalence of sleep disturbance to a cubic polynomial. His fitting solution is not mono-

tonic: prevalence increases East and West of the Beijing meridian, where the prevalence is minimal (optimal). Yet, all meridians are equal; a prime meridian just signals a reference; no outcome can be associated with it. In other words, only a monotonic trend where the prevalence increases or decreases with PTZ would be meaningful.

PTZ is a nice explanatory variable as long as daily rhythms are similar in the dataset, like is the case in USA[4] and Russia[5], but not in the Central European Time zone[6], and most likely not in China. We understand that life in the Xinjiang region is delayed relative to life in Beijing, following the delay in solar ephemerides. In Borisenkov [1, Figure 1B], this would move Xinjiang data 15° to the East per one hour delay, which brings a slight increase of the prevalence in sleep disturbance Eastward, as shown in figure 1.

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Figure 1 The association of position in time zone vs the prevalence of the sleep disturbance in healthcare professionals in China. For the original data the association brings $p = 0.79$ and the null hypothesis “prevalence does not depend on position in time zone” sustains at the standard level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. If Xinjiang data are moved 15° , or one hour phase delay, then $p = 0.31$. If Xinjiang data were moved 30° , then $p = 0.044$; $R^2 = 0.09$ and the null hypothesis would not sustain. The slope would be 0.15 basis points of increase in the prevalence per 15° of change to the East. The regression line and the 95% prediction interval are shown.

version <https://apps.automeris.io/wpd/>. Code can be accessed in <https://github.com/automeris-io/WebPlotDigitizer/releases>

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MANUSCRIPT TIME LINE

On 25 March 2024, the authors were carefully reading Johnson and Malow [3] review paper on Daylight Saving Time when Table 1 caught their attention. They went on to test the references listed on that table and read thoroughly Borisenkov [1]’s analysis. A tweet https://x.com/MartinOlalla_JM/status/1772216191957758178 was posted on the occasion.

The response letter was written and submitted on the spot. The first decision was received on 3 October 2024, 190 days after the initial submission —6 months and 6 days—. The revised version was submitted on 9 October 2024. It was accepted on 11 November 2024, one month later, and 230 days —seven months and sixteen days— from the initial submission. On 13 November 2024 JMMO signed the publishing agreement, the doi was assigned and the Journal Pre-Proofs were published. It was published in final form with full bibliographic details on 19 November 2024.